

STUDIES ON THE ALKALOIDS OF *ALANGIUM LAMARCKII* THW.

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Five new alkaloids have been isolated from the bark of *Alangium lamarckii*. Different salts, estimation of functional groups, determination of molecular formulae and physical properties have been studied. Experiments on the structure of one of the isolated alkaloids, Base B₂, and the ultra-violet and the infra-red absorption spectra of the alkaloids and their degradation products have been described.

The provisional formulae of the alkaloids are: Base B₁ - C₁₉H₂₆O₂N(OCH₃)(OH)₂, m.p. 197-98°; Base B₂ - C₁₇H₂₁O(NCH₃)(OCH₃)₂(OH)₃, m. p. 119-20°; Base B₃ - C₁₆H₁₉ON(OCH₃)(OH)₂, m. p. 160-61°; Base B₄ - C₁₇H₁₉O₂N(OCH₃)₂(OH)₂, m.p. 149-51° and Base B₅ - C₁₉H₂₃O₄N(OCH₃)₂(OH)₂, m.p. 177-79°. The alkaloids are phenolic bases and contain condensed pyrrole nucleus.

Alangium lamarckii Thw. (N.O. Alanguinaceae) is an Indian medicinal plant which has been widely used in India by physicians practising indigenous systems of medicine (Unani & Ayurvedic). Kirtikar and Basu ("Indian Medicinal Plants", L.M. Basu, Allahabad, 1935, Vol. II, p. 1237) have reviewed in detail the therapeutic use of the drug. The bark of the plant is used in leprosy, syphilis and various skin diseases. It is also diaphoretic, antipyretic, anthelmintic and is used in cases of dysentery. Pharmacological actions of crude alkaloidal sulphate were studied by Chopra ("India Medicinal Plants", Patna Univ., 1932, p. 272) and Raymond-Hamlet (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1941, 136, 1011) studied pharmacological actions of an injectable extract.

Dymock ("Pharmacographia Indica", Education Society Press, Bombay, 1893, Vol. II, p. 164) reported the presence of an alkaloid which could not be crystallised. Chopra and Chowhan (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1934, 21, 507) isolated an alkaloid "Alangine" (m.p. 80-82°). Bhargava and Dutt (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, 16A, 328), while working on the seeds of the plant isolated a sterol "Alangol" (C₃₂H₅₄O₇, m.p. 296°). Manjunath *et al.* (*J. Mysore Univ.*, 1942, 3B, 113) also isolated a sterol "Alangol" from the seeds of the plant. Dutt and Parihar (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 23A, 325) were successful in crystallising an alkaloid "Alanginine" (m.p. 205-208°) and prepared a number of salts of the base. The base has been shown to contain one methoxy group and one hydroxy group but no methylimino group. Basu *et al.* (*Ind. J. Pharm.*, 1950, 12, 98) have isolated three more alkaloids, namely, "Akharkantine" (m.p. 146-48°), "Ankoline" (m.p. 110°, empirical formula C₁₇H₂₆O₄N₂) and "Lamarkine" (C₁₃H₁₉O₃N₂, m.p. 60-62°). The alkaloids were freely soluble in benzene and were isolated from the benzene-soluble fraction of the alkaloids. Singh and Tiwari (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 17A, 1) reported the isolation of three bases, viz., "Alangium A" (C₂₁H₂₃O₃N₂, m.p. 219-20°), "Alangium B" (m.p. 105-107°) and "Alanginine C" (m.p. 245-47°). Subbaratnam and Siddiqui (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1956, 15B, 432) isolated from the seed kernels of the plant a methylated alkaloid "Alamarckine" (m.p. 190-91°). From the U.V. and I.R. spectra

of the base the authors have proposed " $C_{24}H_{28}N(OCH_3)_2OH(NCH_3)$ " as the provisional formula of the base. Presence of two double bonds has also been indicated.

As no exhaustive constitutional work appears to have been done on any of the alkaloids, reported so far, nor their pharmacological activity has been explored to any appreciable extent, it has been felt desirable that the drug should be worked upon further for the isolation of different alkaloids from *Alangium L.*, and to study their biological actions and chemical constitutions. The present work has been undertaken with this end in view and five hitherto-unreported alkaloids have been isolated. The method of isolation and purification are based on chromatographic separation. Different salts of the isolated bases have been prepared. Elementary analysis and functional group estimations have been carried out and the molecular formula determined. The alkaloid B_2 was obtained in greater yields and selected for the study of degradation products thereof. Selenium (hydrogenation, soda lime distillation, alkaline hydrolysis and oxidation of the base have been carried out. It has been possible to locate a condensed pyrrole nucleus in the degradation products. The ultraviolet absorption spectra of the alkaloids and their degradation products have been studied and infra-red absorption spectra of the alkaloids B_2 and B_3 have been examined, which support the analytical findings.

The biological properties of the bases have been studied and will be communicated elsewhere. The benzene-soluble bases, reported by previous workers, could not be isolated by the procedure adopted during the present investigation. However, these will be dealt with in a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Extraction and Preliminary Separation.—The powdered bark (20 kg.) of the plant (in No. 60 mesh) was moistened with 1% HCl and packed in glass percolators and extracted with 1% HCl by percolation process. The acid percolate (130 litres) was filtered and the filtrate made alkaline to litmus with a 10% aqueous solution of sodium carbonate. A voluminous chocolate-brown precipitate separated. The mixture was filtered under suction and the precipitate after being washed with little water was dried under vacuum and kept as precipitate "A" for further investigation. The filtrate from above was made distinctly acidic with H_2SO_4 (dil.) and the alkaloids were precipitated by Dragendorff's reagent. The deep orange-coloured precipitate was washed with water and dried in vacuo. The alkaloidal bismuth iodide was treated with dry acetone and the acetone solution decomposed with silver carbonate. The filtrate after removal of bismuth and silver by treatment with H_2S was marked "Solution B_1 ". The residual alkaloidal bismuth iodide, which was not soluble in acetone, was dissolved in alcohol and the filtrate decomposed with silver carbonate, and treated as before. This alcoholic solution was marked "Solution B_2 ".

Isolation of Alkaloid from "Solution B_1 ".—As no crystalline material was obtained from solution B_1 , it was purified by redragendorffing and decomposing with silver carbonate as before. The residue was then dissolved in alcohol and passed over a column of alumina (55×3 cm, packed with 400 g. of B.D.H. alumina). The chro-

matogram obtained after developing with 95% alcohol was composed of an upper dark brown band (3 cm), followed by a lower deep yellow band (30 cm). The chromatogram was eluted with 95% alcohol and the lower yellow band was completely washed out from the column and received in the eluate fraction (300 c.c.). The dark brown band was found to contain non-alkaloidal resinous impurities, and was therefore rejected. The eluate was filtered and evaporated to dryness under vacuo, and the residue on prolonged refrigeration and crystallisation from acetone-ether mixture (1:3) afforded a pale yellow, amorphous mass, melting at 197-98°. The amorphous mass on repeated crystallisations from absolute alcohol yielded shining brown granules of the pure base, B₁ (5.5 g.), the melting point of which was found to be 197-98°.

Isolation of Alkaloid from "Solution B₂".—The solution B₂ containing alcohol-soluble alkaloids was also redragendorffed and decomposed with silver carbonate. It was then purified by passing over a column of alumina (55 × 3 cm, packed with 400 g. of B.D.H. alumina). On developing the chromatogram with alcohol, there appeared a dark brown band of 2.5 cm, followed by a lower pale yellow band of 21.5 cm. The column was eluted with 95% alcohol to wash away the lower pale yellow band. The eluate fraction (400 c.c.) was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure; the residue was taken up in methanol and the alkaloid was reprecipitated with ether. After repeating the precipitation of the alkaloid, finally the precipitated base was repeatedly crystallised from absolute ethanol at 0° (in refrigerator). This yielded another pure base, B₂ (7.5 g.), m.p. 119-20°.

Isolation of Alkaloids from the Precipitate "A".—The precipitate "A" containing crude alkaloids, precipitated by sodium carbonate, was digested with hot alcohol and filtered. The alcohol-insoluble portion was labelled "A₁" and the alcoholic filtrate, "A₂", was poured in a thin stream into a large volume of ethyl acetate, and the ethyl acetate-insoluble fraction was separated by filtration and labelled "A₃". The ethyl acetate filtrate "E" was concentrated and fractionally precipitated with water into two water-insoluble fractions, "E₁" and "E₂", and the filtrate after separation of fraction "E₂" was evaporated; the residue was labelled "E₃".

Precipitate "A₁" obtained was not sufficient and therefore no attempts for crystallisation could be made.

Precipitate "E₁" was dissolved in alcohol (50 c.c.) and the solution was poured in a large excess of water whereupon the precipitate reappeared. This process was repeated several times to remove water-soluble impurities, and a brown amorphous residue was obtained. It was digested with hot methyl alcohol and the small insoluble portion was rejected. The methanolic solution was treated with animal charcoal and finally the filtrate on refrigeration over a long period yielded a brown crystalline material. It was repeatedly crystallised from methanol to yield a new base, "B₃", m.p. 160-61°.

Precipitate "E₂" was not considered sufficient for further work.

Treatment of Residue "E₃".—The residue was dissolved in 95% alcohol and ether was added to it in small portions. A dark brown amorphous precipitate separated, leaving the supernatant liquid deep brown in colour. The precipitate was washed with ether. The decantate and the ethereal washings gave on evaporation a negligible amount of

a residue. Several attempts to crystallise the ether-insoluble fraction from different solvents did not succeed. It was then dissolved in alcohol and acetone mixture (1:1) and passed through 420 g. of alumina, packed in a column (55 × 3 cm). The chromatogram was first developed with acetone and then with a mixture of acetone and alcohol (3:1). At this stage the elution was terminated and the chromatogram was composed of the following bands from its upper end to lower end:—(1) Dark brown band, 2.5 cm. (2) Pale brown band, 4.5 cm. (3) Yellowish brown band, 4 cm. (4) Light orange-red band, 6 cm. (5) Pale yellow band, 18 cm. (6) White band, 14 cm. (7) Deep yellow band, 2 mm. The bands were separated from the column by means of a spatula and each one of them was digested with hot alcohol and the alcoholic extracts were evaporated. The residue obtained from the 4th orange-red band appeared to be more pure and free from resinous matter, while those obtained from the other bands were resinous and also very small in quantity, and therefore could not be worked further. The residue from the 4th band was redissolved in acetone and passed over a column of alumina (20 × 3 cm), the adsorbent was removed and digested with alcohol. The alcoholic solution on prolonged refrigeration deposited an orange-red microcrystalline precipitate, which, on repeated crystallisation from alcohol-ether mixture, yielded a pure new crystalline base, "B₁", m.p. 149-50°.

Treatment of Precipitate "A₃".—The precipitate containing ethyl acetate-insoluble fraction of the alkaloids was extracted with alcohol and filtered. A little insoluble residue was rejected. The alcoholic filtrate was concentrated (150 c.c.) and poured in distilled water (800 c.c.) whereupon some precipitate appeared which was separated by filtration. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator; the residue (25.5 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (20 c.c.) and the solution was added to 200 c.c. of acetone whereupon a dark brown precipitate separated. The supernatant liquid was decanted and evaporated to dryness in vacuo. The residue (23.5 g.) was dissolved in 100 c.c. of acetone and alcohol mixture (1:1) and passed through 450 g. of alumina, packed in a column (60 × 3 cm). The chromatogram was developed with acetone till 600 c.c. of eluate was collected; the development was satisfactory. The chromatogram was composed of the following bands:—(1) Dark brown band, 2 cm. (2) Pale brown band, 23 cm. (3) Deep orange-red band, 31 cm. (4) Pale yellow band, 10 cm. (5) Deep yellow band, 2 cm. The fifth deep yellow band was washed away in the acetone eluate, which on evaporation under vacuo yielded a resinous dark brown residue. It was not worked further. The column was partially dried under suction and the different bands were separated by means of a long glass spatula. Each of them was extracted with hot alcohol and the alcoholic extracts after filtration and evaporation under vacuo yielded residues from the respective bands. Out of all the residues, the one obtained from the third deep orange-red band was more in quantity (11.2 g.) and appeared to be free from associated resinous impurities and, therefore this was taken for purification; the other residues were not worked further.

The residue (11.2 g.), obtained above, was dissolved in alcohol and again passed through a column of alumina (45 × 3 cm). After satisfactory development of the chromatogram with acetone-alcohol mixture (1:1), the column was dried and the adsorbent removed. The alkaloid was extracted from the adsorbent with hot alcohol and the

alcoholic extract (2.5 litres) was evaporated to dryness in vacuo. Attempts to crystallise the base from this residue by fractional crystallisation using different solvents did not meet with success. Therefore, a little quantity of the residue was dissolved in 0.5% H_2SO_4 and the base was precipitated with Dragendorff's reagent and decomposed with silver carbonate as usual. But it was found that the base was decomposed in this process. In another trial the base was precipitated as insoluble reineckate and decomposed with silver carbonate. This process proved successful. Therefore, the remainder of the alkaloidal residue was extracted with 0.5% H_2SO_4 and precipitated with a saturated aqueous solution of ammonium reineckate; the insoluble alkaloidal reineckate was separated by filtration. The precipitate was dissolved in acetone and decomposed with sufficient silver carbonate till a portion of the mixture on filtration gave negative test with silver nitrate solution. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuo and refrigerated for a week whereupon a deep orange-red crystalline mass separated. On repeated crystallisations from absolute alcohol, it yielded pure alkaloid "B₅", m.p. 177-79°.

CHART I

Scheme for separation of alkaloids.

TABLE I

Melting points of the salts of alkaloids.

Salts.	Base B ₁ .	Base B ₂ .	Base B ₃ .	Base B ₄ .	Base B ₅ .
Hydrochloride	228-29°	188°	181°	199°	208°
Picrate	166-67°	139° (decomp.)	143-45° (decomp.)	142°	91°
Picolonate	205-10°	164°	243° (,,)	175°	199°
Platinichloride	Darkens at 235° and melts at 272° (decomp.)	Darkens at 207° and melts at 215° (decomp.)	Darkens at 191° and melts at 232° (decomp.)	205° (decomp.)	249° (decomp.)
Aurichloride	Darkens at 220° ; melts at 235° (decomp.)	Darkens at 195° ; melts at 203° (decomp.)	292° (decomp.)	182° (,,)	151° (,,)
Bismuth iodide	194-95° (decomp.)	215° ,,	265° ,,	175° ,,	225° ,,
Hydro-iodide	213-15° ,,	189° ,,	227° ,,	174° ,,	194° ,,
Rcineckate	Charred at 249°	Darkens at 235° and melts at 266° (decomp.).	Charred at 245°	Charred at 248°	Charred at 305°

Solubility of the Alkaloids.—All the alkaloids were found to be freely soluble in ethyl alcohol and in 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution. The solubility in the latter indicates the presence of phenolic hydroxy groups.

The alkaloids, when treated with an alcoholic solution of ferric chloride, developed a yellowish green to pale violet coloration. This reaction also indicates the presence of phenolic hydroxyl groups.

Molecular Formulae.—The elementary analyses for C, H and N were done by the usual micro-combustion methods. Since the bases were insoluble in camphor, the molecular weights were determined by the ebullioscopic method using alcohol as the solvent. Assuming the bases to be mono-acidic, the molecular weights were also determined by the ignition of the platonic chloride derivatives of the bases. The analytical figures leading to the molecular formulae are compared in Table II.

TABLE II

Base with m.p.	Mol. formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		%Nitrogen.		M. W. by		
		Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	* B.P.	† PtCl ₄	Calc. formulae wts.
B ₁ (197-98°)	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₅ N	65.75	65.79	8.494	8.51	3.835	3.83	356	370	365
B ₂ (119-20°)	C ₂₇ H ₄₅ O ₈ N	66.53	66.99	8.831	8.97	2.935	2.93	496	483	477
B ₃ (160-61°)	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	66.67	66.42	7.843	7.79	4.575	4.63	302	310	306
B ₄ (149-51°)	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ O ₇ N	59.84	59.75	7.087	7.10	3.675	3.65	391	381	381
B ₅ (177-79°)	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	59.29	59.21	7.295	7.28	3.294	3.28	429	430	425
			59.32		7.25		3.27			

* Mean of three readings.

† Mean of two readings.

TABLE III

Hydrochlorides of the alkaloids (analysis by combustion).

Base.	Mol. formula.	Calc.				Found.			
		%C.	%H.	%N.	%Cl.	%C.	%H.	%N.	%Cl.
B ₁	C ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₆ NCl	59.78	7.97	3.48	8.24	59.43	7.84	3.46	8.86
B ₂	C ₂₇ H ₄₄ O ₆ NCl	63.10	8.57	2.72	6.91	63.25	8.59	2.73	6.95
B ₃	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ O ₄ NCl	59.57	7.30	4.12	10.36	59.22	7.28	4.13	10.45
B ₄	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O ₇ NCl	54.63	6.70	3.35	8.50	54.78	6.73	3.39	8.67
B ₅	C ₂₁ H ₃₂ O ₆ NCl	54.61	6.93	3.03	7.60	54.72	6.97	3.07	7.55

Estimation of Functional Groups.—Hydroxy groups were estimated by Peterson's method (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1943, 15, 227). Estimation of methoxyl groups was carried out by Zeisel's method and N.Me group was estimated by Herzig and Meyer's method. The number of functional groups in different alkaloids are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Base.	Mol. formula.	No. of OH groups.	No. of OMe groups.	No. of N.Me groups.
B ₁	C ₂₀ H ₃₁ O ₅ N	2	1	Nil
B ₂	C ₂₇ H ₄₃ O ₆ N	3	2	1
B ₃	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ N	2	1	Nil
B ₄	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ O ₇ N	2	2	Nil
B ₅	C ₂₁ H ₃₁ O ₆ N	2	2	Nil

Constitutional Investigations

Out of the five alkaloids, the base B₁ (C₂₀H₃₁O₅N, m.p. 119-20°) was obtained in sufficient yields, and it was subjected to constitutional studies. It has been shown that the base B₂ contains two OMe groups, three OH groups and one N.Me group. Solution of the base in acetone did not develop any coloration with a solution of sodium nitroprusside (Rimini's test). Similarly, the alcoholic solution of the base to which a freshly prepared solution of acetaldehyde was added also showed no coloration with sodium nitroprusside (Simon's test). These reactions indicate that the nitrogen atom is not primary or secondary, but of tertiary nature, having a methyl group attached to it.

Selenium Dehydrogenation.—A mixture of the base B₁ (2 g.) and selenium powder (6 g.) was heated in a current of dry hydrogen and the receiving bulbs were surrounded with crushed ice. The temperature was kept at 280° and later raised to 340°. Four fractions were collected: (1) basic portion contained in the alcoholic hydrochloric acid trap bulbs, (2) basic aqueous yellow liquid in the receiving bulb, (3) water-insoluble basic substance collected in the side tube and (4) selenium melt in the distilling bulb.

Fraction 1: The acid liquid on evaporation left a white crystalline deposit which was found to be ammonium chloride.

Fraction 2: This yellow liquid was alkaline to litmus and emitted piperidine-like odour. It may be mentioned here that the odour of pyrrolidine is quite resembling that of piperidine. Due to very low yield it was not possible to dry the liquid and note

its boiling point. Therefore its picrate was prepared by adding an aqueous saturated solution of picric acid and warming. The picrate crystallised on concentration and refrigeration, and after being washed with little water, the crystals melted at 112-113°. The melting points of the picrates of pyrrolidine, pyrrole and piperidine are 112°, 69° and 152° respectively.

Fraction 3: It could not be worked further for any conclusive results.

Fraction 4: Selenium-melt in the distilling bulb was extracted with ether and then with hot alcohol. The alcoholic extract was evaporated and the residue was taken up in ether and the combined ethereal extract of the melt was shaken with 5% H₂SO₄ to remove any basic fraction. After washing the ethereal layer with distilled water, it was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated. On refrigeration overnight a few white crystals separated which on centrifuging and subsequent crystallisation from absolute alcohol yielded 6 mg. of the crystalline material. It melted at 134-135° (micro-melting). The ultraviolet absorption of the solution of this substance in alcohol was taken using Unicam S. P. 500 spectrophotometer, and since it showed an absorption maximum at $\lambda = 280 \text{ m}\mu$ (Fig. 1) a carbonyl group was suspected. This was confirmed as the substance gave yellow precipitate with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine reagent. No further work on this substance could be done.

Soda-lime Distillation.—Soda-lime distillation in a current of dry nitrogen evolved white fumes which gave positive pine-splinter reaction, indicating pyrrole type of compounds. The aqueous liquid collected in the receiving bulb was smelling like pyrrolidine. It gave positive isatin reaction and a red coloration with *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde solution, indicating pyrrole or indole type of compounds. The remainder of the distillate was made alkaline with dilute NaOH solution and an 1% aqueous solution of sodium nitroprusside was added when it acquired a brownish colour. It was acidified with acetic acid and the reddish brown colour was extracted with chloroform, indicating presence of a pyrrole body. This test recommended by Herzfeld (Allen's Commercial Organic Analysis, J. & A. Churchill, London, 1938, Vol. V, pp. 648-651) distinguishes pyrrole from indole, which under similar conditions shows violet-blue colour which is not extracted with chloroform.

Alkaline Hydrolysis.—The base B₂ (1.5 g.) was refluxed with 10% alcoholic KOH (50 c.c.) for 6 hours. The liquid was filtered, acidified with H₂SO₄ (dil.) and extracted with ether in a liquid-liquid continuous extraction apparatus. The ether extract containing the non-basic fraction was dried and the solvent removed. The residue was dissolved in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and passed over a column of alumina and was eluted with alcohol. The eluate yielded white needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 113-114°, which did not react with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, showing absence of carbonyl group. Due to low yields only its U. V. absorption spectra could only be taken. For working out the basic fraction the aqueous liquid was rendered alkaline and shaken with chloroform. On evaporation no crystalline material could be obtained, but a picrate melting 147-48° could be prepared.

Oxidation.—The base B₂ (2 g.) was dissolved in dry acetone and carefully oxidised with KMnO₄ (2.5 g.) at room temperature for 14 days. The mixture was filtered and the residue extracted with dry acetone. The acetone extract was evaporated in vacuo

and taken up in chloroform and later in alcohol and purified through an alumina column. From the eluate a needle-shaped colorless crystalline mass melting at 109° was obtained. Its solution in neutral alcohol was acidic to litmus and liberated iodine from a mixture of potassium iodide and iodate. Since the quantity was too small for any analytical work, it was mixed with soda-lime and heated over a microburner. The vapours gave positive pine splinter test.

Spectrophotometric Studies.—The alkaloids were dissolved in alcohol and absorption measurements were taken between λ 210 and λ 540 $m\mu$ on a Unicam spectrophotometer (S.P. 500). The absorption spectra of the alkaloids are shown in Fig. 1. The spectra of B_1 and B_2 show absorption maxima at λ 283 $m\mu$ and λ 405 $m\mu$. Both the spectra are similar. The spectrum of alkaloid B_3 also resembles in some respects. There is a general absorption below λ 230 $m\mu$, which may be due to hydroxy groups. The spectra of alkaloids B_3 and B_4 are similar. In general, the U. V. absorption spectra of the alkaloids speak of their similarity in chromophoric functions.

FIG. 1

Absorption Spectra of Degradation Products.—The fractions taken for measurements were: (a) non-basic substance (m.p. $134-35^{\circ}$) from selenium dehydrogenation of base B_2 , (b) non-basic substance (m.p. $113-114^{\circ}$) from alkaline hydrolysis of base B_3 , and (c) basic water-insoluble substance from soda-lime distillation of base B_3 . The absorption spectra of the alcoholic solutions of the above fractions were taken between λ 220 and λ 500 $m\mu$. The absorptions are represented in Fig. 2. The spectrum of fraction A shows absorption maxima at λ 230, λ 280 and λ 480 $m\mu$. It appears to be a complex

substance. The peak at λ 280 $m\mu$ may be attributed to carbonyl group. The spectra of fractions B and C do not show any characteristic peaks.

FIG. 2

Infra-red Absorption Spectra of Alkaloids.—Only base B₂ and B₃ were selected for the I.R. spectra. Their solid spectra were taken on a Grubb-Parson spectrometer with NaCl prism, between λ 2 and λ 14 μ . The I.R. absorption spectra of base B₂ and B₃ show similarity in their structures. The absorption maxima at λ 3.42 μ may be due to alkyl groups. Maxima at λ 6.53 and λ 6.95 μ indicate potential carbonyl functions. Absorption in the region λ 7 - λ 8.5 μ indicate methoxyl groups. Unsaturation and complex polycyclic structures are indicated by absorptions in the region λ 9 - λ 13 μ . The I.R. spectra of B₂ and B₃ are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively. The I.R. records were obtained at the National Chemical Laboratory of India, Poona.

FIG. 3

CONCLUSION

Qualitative tests, solubility and analytical data of the alkaloids indicate that all the alkaloids are phenolic bases containing methoxy groups. The alkaloid B₂ (m.p. 119-20°) on selenium dehydrogenation yields a ketonic body, showing positive reaction with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine reagent. The pure base, however, does not exhibit positive reaction with this reagent. The picrate of the basic substance from selenium dehydrogenation resembles pyrrolidine picrate, but its exact identity could not be established. Soda-lime distillation was attempted to locate the heterocyclic nucleus present in the molecule. But this could reveal only a pyrrole or a condensed pyrrole nucleus. Oxidation with KMnO_4 afforded an acid containing pyrrole nucleus, and alkaline hydrolysis yielded a non-basic substance (m.p. 113-14°) and a basic picrate (m.p. 147-48°), which could not throw much light on constitution. U.V. and I. R. absorption spectra show similarity in structural make up of the alkaloids. But no definite conclusion regarding the nucleus could be derived from the spectra. In fact, it is necessary to isolate one of the products of degradation in good yield for further work.

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